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CYGNUS-Oz: Australian R&D for a future CYGNUS network of directional dark matter detectors

L. J. McKie

Department of Nuclear Physics and Accelerator Applications,
The Australian National University
ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics

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Abstract

The detection limits for WIMP-nucleon scattering are approaching the neutrino fog where coherent neutrino-nucleus scattering will form an irreducible background for many of the dark matter detector technologies currently in use. CYGNUS is a network of international research groups who aim to use directional detection as a means to penetrate the neutrino fog. Their current focus is R&D aimed at optimising gas Time Projection Chambers (TPCs) to achieve low energy thresholds and excellent nuclear recoil track reconstruction, so as to image the recoil tracks caused by WIMP interactions. The long-term goal is to combine results from a network of underground gas TPCs to make a large-scale distributed observatory for nuclear and electron recoils.

Australian researchers have recently formalised the CYGNUS-Oz collaboration so as to concentrate the Australian CYGNUS efforts. CYGNUS-1, a prototype gas TPC has been developed with the ability to handle mixes of up to 3 different gases, and a Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM) amplification stage with wire readout to observe the ionisation track created by a recoiling nucleus within the gas volume. These proceedings will introduce the CYGNUS-Oz collaboration as well as present the initial results of CYGNUS-1.

1 Introduction

In modern cosmology, significant amounts of dark matter are required to explain astronomical observations. Experimental searches for the theoretically well motivated dark matter candidate, the Weakly Interacting Massive Particle (WIMP), whose theoretical mass spans a broad parameter space between 100 MeV-1 TeV, remain inconclusive [1]. This has prompted direct detection experiments to increase in scale and sensitivity within this mass region with multi tonne-year exposures in order to probe smaller cross sections. This added sensitivity renders detectors susceptible to new backgrounds such as the so called *neutrino fog*, where neutrinos interact with the target nuclei via the recently observed Coherent Elastic neutrino-Nucleus Scattering (CE ν NS) process in a manner that can mimic the expected WIMP signal [4]. The WIMP parameter space within the neutrino fog was previously believed to be beyond the accessible search limit.

The limited means to differentiate background neutrino events from true dark matter signals limits discovery potential using a conventional detection system. A proposed method to distinguish between these events is to develop detectors sensitive to the direction of the signal, since background signals such as solar neutrinos can be reconstructed to point back towards the sun, while a dark matter signal within most dark matter models will be reconstructed to identify the direction of travel through the dark matter halo [7].

The most mature direction sensitive technology is the gas Time Projection Chamber (TPC) that consists of a sensitive volume of target gas subjected to an electric field. When incident dark matter or neutrinos collide with a target nucleus, this momentum transfer will cause the nucleus to recoil ionising a short ($\mathcal{O}(mm)$) recoil track. This ionisation track, subjected to the electric field, will then drift to a readout plane where a two-dimensional signal can be observed and the third dimension reconstructed from the arrival times of the drifted charge. CYGNUS, a global proto-collaboration involving many research institutions, currently operates TPCs in a research and development capacity, in addition to previously setting WIMP search limits with detectors at the m³ scale [3].

This proceeding will briefly outline the current research being conducted by the international CYGNUS proto-collaboration, followed by an introduction to the newly formed CYGNUS-Oz collaboration. The proceeding will conclude with an update of the research and development currently underway within the CYGNUS-Oz collaboration with a focus on experimental work performed with the CYGNUS-1 prototype.

2 CYGNUS proto-collaboration

The CYGNUS proto-collaboration has identified the potential of directional detector technology and seeks to develop a network of direction-sensitive dark matter detectors in order to resolve an unambiguous dark matter signal within the neutrino fog. The current research of the collaboration has been focused on the development of gas TPC technology and the scalability of such detectors.

Efforts to scale the detector volume for a large scale dark matter search encounter engineering challenges due to diffusion of the charge carriers as they move to the readout plane, which has prompted significant research into the gases used within TPCs. The recent discovery of Negative Ion Drift (NID) gases, such as Sulfur Hexafluoride (SF₆) and Carbon Disulfide (CS₂), have been proposed as a potential solution to minimise diffusion [6] but limited experience and understanding of the mechanisms governing these gases have delayed their widespread adoption.

Figure 1: Projected WIMP Sensitivity plots for a direction-sensitive gas TPC of various target volumes, interaction channels and detector energy thresholds. Figure from [9]

Separately, TPCs have seen rapid development in the previous two decades due to the widespread accessibility of micro-patterned electronics allowing the development of highly segmented readouts and gain stages for ionisation detectors. Many of these micro-patterned components such as Gas Electron Multipliers (GEMs) [2] were optimised for conventional electron drift gases, whereas NID gases may produce adverse results and require further investigation before large scale direction-sensitive detectors can be readily implemented. Alternate readout techniques such as those based on optical sensors, or a combination of multiple readout regimes, are also being investigated to determine the ideal readout for a large detector [9].

As presented in figure 1, with careful target gas choices and reasonable detector thresholds a direction-sensitive detector could set world leading spin-dependent WIMP search limits across the mass range with a 10 m³ sensitive volume; this is an achievable medium term goal. Larger detector volumes would be required to probe into the neutrino fog, however, the directional information recovered would be invaluable to new physics across multiple fields [10].

3 CYGNUS-Oz

CYGNUS-Oz is an Australian research collaboration formalised in early 2023. This collaboration consists of Australian research institutions seeking to investigate this new detection capability with the eventual goal of deploying a large scale detector within Australia. The efforts of CYGNUS-Oz have thus been loosely defined in three focus areas, Experimental Research and Development, Data Analysis and Event reconstruction and finally directional detector theory.

The Experimental Research and Development branch of CYGNUS-Oz is developing prototype gas TPCs, such as CYGNUS-1 discussed below, with the intent to eventually deploy a larger scale TPC in Australia as part of the CYGNUS global network. This research and development process, spread across multiple institutions, involves both fundamental research into gas properties, such as NID scintillation, charge-light ratios and NID coupling cross-sections as well as combined charge-optical readout systems. In addition, this group is developing the supporting infrastructure, such as a gas recirculation system, required to operate these detectors over extended periods in remote locations such as the Stawell Underground Physics Labora-

Figure 2: SUPL has a comparable depth to other international underground laboratories (left) but due to the southern hemisphere location has an increased daily inclination to the constellation Cygnus (right) making it an interesting location for a direction-sensitive detector (figure from [8]).

tory (SUPL) (see figure 2).

Independent of the final readout technology, the data collected by a long term direction-sensitive dark matter experiment poses analysis challenges due to the depth of information for adequate direction reconstruction. To provide a sense of the data required in order to reconstruct precision directional information, high granularity readouts with spatial resolutions of $\mathcal{O}(100 \mu\text{m})$, timing resolutions of $\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ ns})$ and dE/dx information along the entire track length for head-tail sense. Event reconstruction for a direction sensitive detector is thus comparatively complex when compared to other experiments due to the data rich nature of the observation making it an ideal candidate for machine learning techniques. This has prompted a dedicated reconstruction group to both model and develop analysis methods in preparation for future experiments.

The CYGNUS-Oz theory group is focused on investigating the discovery reach of using such detectors, and how best to implement them for various applications. Within the dark matter context, gas TPCs show excellent promise within the conventional WIMP halo models but the directional nature also allows to probe alternate models not usually accessible such as dark matter streams [5]. When gas TPCs probe within the neutrino fog, these experiments will be able to make meaningful contributions to both neutrino physics and astrophysics by allowing solar neutrino energy spectra to be measured. The development of detectors sensitive to directional information at this energy regime remains quite novel, and has opened doors to other branches of physics with experiments already in development to measure fundamental interactions such as the Migdal effect.

4 CYGNUS-1

CYGNUS-1, see Figure 3, is a prototype gas TPC developed at the Australian National University. CYGNUS-1 serves as an experimental platform for a variety of investigations concerning gas properties and readouts. The intended outcomes of this detector are to demonstrate high-quality directional track reconstruction with a gas TPC, develop supporting infrastructure, investigate gas mixtures (including those employing NID) and assess the potential for a composite readout for future large scale direction-sensitive technologies. In order to accomplish these goals

Figure 3: CYGNUS-1 (right) is a prototype gas TPC with a combined charge-optical readout. The PMT, mounted in a PVC light shroud observes both primary and secondary scintillation light separated by time in the drift volume. Charge signals observed by the MWPC (left) are coincident with only the secondary PMT pulse.

CYGNUS-1 has been designed to host a suite of evolving readout configurations including a combined charge-optical readout as discussed below.

CYGNUS-1 has an 18 cm long drift region that can be filled with up to triple gas mixtures at operating pressures between 10 and 760 Torr. An ^{241}Am source was mounted externally to the field cage for observation of the 59 keV photon only. Optical measurements of prompt and secondary scintillation light (see figure 4) within the drift region are observed by a Hamamatsu H10828 Photomultiplier tube (PMT) coupled to a windowed flange at the top of the prototype that observes the gas volume and the GEM through a mesh cathode. A single thick GEM is used for ionisation charge amplification which sits 6 mm above a 10 wire Multiwire Proportional Counter (MWPC) with a wire pitch of 10 mm. Charge readout of individual MWPC wires is conducted by Cremat CR-110 charge sensitive preamplifiers and signals are recorded by a CAEN 2740 digitiser triggering on the PMT signal (due to RF noise on the charge channels). Triggering on the optical channel has confined experimental gas mixtures to those with a high scintillating component such as CF_4 , however measurements were also taken with wavelength shifting additives such as Ar:N_2 , albeit with mixed results due to suspected gas impurities.

Figure 4: Time difference between primary and secondary scintillation light observed by PMT. A peak is observed in measurements with an external ^{241}Am source at a known height above the GEM. Measurements of drift velocities allow for fiducialisation in the z-dimension within CYGNUS-1.

4.1 Future Work

Work has already begun on an upgraded version of CYGNUS-1. The most significant upgrade will be the addition of an image-intensified CCD (ICCD) camera readout to the base of the detector. This will provide high resolution x-y planar observations within CYGNUS-1 and allow for 3D track reconstruction within the detector for the first time.

Observations of operational instabilities attributed to gas impurities warrant further study to achieve long term detector stability. This challenge is not unique to the dark matter community and will become more pertinent as the potential of these detectors is realised. Furthermore the environmental impact of specific target gases, such as SF₆, has prompted a shift towards more sustainable gases, or re-circulation, within the high energy particle physics community presenting future opportunities for collaboration.

5 Conclusion

CYGNUS-Oz is an Australian research collaboration interested in developing a direction-sensitive detectors using gas TPCs. A research and development program has been implemented within CYGNUS-Oz to develop prototype gas TPCs in order to study target gas properties and readout technologies. CYGNUS-1 is the first prototype and has identified gas impurities as a significant issue prompting design changes for the next prototype currently under construction that will also incorporate an ICCD camera for x-y reconstruction.

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